

DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF STABILITY INDICATING ANALYTICAL METHOD FOR ESTIMATION OF ACEBROPHYLLINE AND ERDOSTEINE IN SYNTHETIC MIXTURE

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ABSTRACT

A simple, precise, and accurate stability indicating RP-HPLC method was developed for the estimation of Acebrophylline and Erdosteine in synthetic mixture. The quantification was carried out using Zorbax C18 column (250 mm x 4.6 mm x 5 µm) and mobile phase comprised of 0.1 % Formic acid: Phosphate Buffer pH 4.8: Methanol in proportion of 60:15:25% v/v. The Flow rate was adjusted to 1.0 mL/min and the effluent was monitored at 220 nm using PDA detector. The retention time of Acebrophylline and Erdosteine was found to be 19.807 min 8.907 min respectively. The methods were validated in terms of specificity, linearity, precision, and accuracy, limit of detection, limit of quantification and robustness. The percentage assay was found to be 100.206 % for Acebrophylline and 100.154 % for Erdosteine in RP-HPLC method. Acebrophylline and Erdosteine were subjected to stress condition like Acid, Base, Oxidative, Thermal & Photo condition. Acceptable range of

degradation was observed in Acebrophylline and Erdosteine in all the condition. The degradation products were well resolved from the pure drug with significant differences in their retention time. Thus, the proposed method enables rapid quantification and simultaneous estimation of

the Acebrophylline and Erdosteine drug without any interference of excipients. So, the developed and validated method can be used for routine analysis of Acebrophylline and Erdosteine in synthetic mixture.

KEYWORDS: Acebrophylline, Erdosteine, RP-HPLC, Stability indicating, Validation.

INTRODUCTION

Obstructive airway diseases such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and chronic bronchitis are common respiratory conditions characterized by airflow limitation and excessive mucus production, leading to symptoms like cough, breathlessness, and recurrent infections. COPD, a progressive disorder strongly associated with smoking, air pollution, and occupational exposures, involves chronic bronchitis and emphysema as its main forms, with pathological changes including inflammation, mucus gland hypertrophy, and destruction of alveolar walls.^[1,2]

Acebrophylline

Acebrophylline is a xanthine derivative with bronchodilator and mucolytic properties. It relaxes bronchial smooth muscles to improve airflow, reduces airway inflammation, and decreases mucus viscosity, making it effective in COPD, chronic bronchitis, and asthma.^[3]

Erdosteine

Erdosteine is a mucolytic and antioxidant agent that breaks disulfide bonds in mucus, improving expectoration. It also exhibits anti-inflammatory and anti-adhesive effects, reducing bacterial colonization and the frequency of COPD exacerbations.^[4]

Fig. 1: Structure of Acebrophylline and Erdosteine.

The literature review reveals that few analytical methods were reported like RP-HPLC methods^[5], Spectrophotometric method^[6], HPTLC^[7], UHPLC^[8] and UPLC^[9] in single or in Combination with other drug. But no method is reported for stability study & RP-HPLC. Hence present study aimed to develop a new Stability Indicating analytical method for

estimation of Acebrophylline & Erdosteine in synthetic mixture suitable for routine quality control analysis.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemicals and Reagents

Table 1: List of chemicals and reagents.

Material	Company	Grade
Water	Merck	AR Grade
Methanol	Merck	AR Grade
Acetonitrile	Merck	AR Grade
Formic acid	Finar	AR Grade
Glacial acetic acid	Finar	AR Grade

Preparation of Stock solution

Preparation of Stock Solution of Acebrophylline and Erdosteine (1000 ppm)

Accurately weighed 100 mg of drug and transferred into 100 ml volumetric flask. To this, 20 ml of methanol was added and dissolved by sonication. The solution was diluted up to the mark with methanol and used as a stock solution.

Preparation of mobile phase

0.1 % formic acid prepared by dissolving 0.1 ml formic acid into 100 mL HPLC grade water. Diluted 100ml of 0.5M potassium dihydrogen phosphate to 800ml with water, pH of the solution was adjusted to 4.8 with diluted sodium hydroxide.

Forced Degradation Study

1) Acid Degradation

Stock solution 1 ml + 1 mL 0.1 N HCl in 10 ml volumetric flask. Kept for 40 min on table top at room temperature. Neutralized with 1 mL 0.1 N NaOH. Volume made with diluent and injected into HPLC.

2) Base Degradation

Standard stock solution 1 ml + 1 mL 0.1 N NaOH in 10 ml volumetric flask. Kept for 30 min on table top at room temperature. Neutralized with 1 mL 0.1 N HCl. Volume made with diluent and injected into HPLC.

3) Oxidation Degradation

Standard stock solution of 1 ml + 1 mL 3% H₂O₂ in 10 ml volumetric flask. Kept for 15 min at RT. Volume made with diluent and injected into HPLC.

4) Photolytic Degradation

Sample and standard solutions were kept in sunlight for 90min. Volume was made with diluent. Then injected into HPLC.

5) Thermal Degradation

Thermal degradation was performed by keeping API and samples in hot air oven at 80 °C 10 min.

METHOD VALIDATION^[10]

1) Linearity and Range (n=3)

The linearity for Acebrophylline and Erdosteine were assessed by analysis of combined standard solution in range of 500-1500µg/ml. Correlation co-efficient for calibration curve Acebrophylline and Erdosteine was found to be 0.9999 and 0.9999 respectively.

2) Precision

Precision was evaluated at three levels: intermediate precision (intraday precision), reproducibility (interday precision), and repeatability. The solution containing 1000.0 µg/ml of Acebrophylline and Erdosteine was injected six times for repeatability study. Intermediate precision study was performed by injecting 500, 1000, 1500 µg/ml of Acebrophylline and Erdosteine solutions three times for each aliquot. The %RSD for precision was calculated.

3) Limit of Detection and Limit of Quantitation

The LOD and LOQ were separately determined from calibration curve. Calibration curve was repeated for three times and the standard deviation (SD) of the intercept was calculated. Then LOD and LOQ were calculated using following equation:

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 * \sigma/S \text{ and } \text{LOQ} = 10 * \sigma/S$$

Where, σ = Standard deviation of Y-intercepts, S = Mean slope of calibration curve.

4) Accuracy

The accuracy of the method was assessed using the standard addition technique, where a known amount of the working standard was spiked at three concentration levels: 80%, 100%,

and 120%. Each solution was injected in triplicate and the recovery was calculated by measuring peak areas.

5) Robustness

The robustness of the analytical procedure was evaluated to assess its ability to remain unaffected by minor but deliberate variations in method parameters, ensuring its reliability during routine use. Robustness testing was conducted (n=3) by altering key parameters, including:

Flow rate of the mobile phase (± 0.2 ml/min)

pH (± 2)

Mobile phase composition ($\pm 0.2\%$).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Optimized Chromatographic Conditions

Agilent HPLC system was used for method development, degradation studies and validation. Data acquisition was performed on HPLC. The separations were achieved on select Agilent Zorbax C18 (250 \times 4.6 mm, 5 μ m). The column was maintained at room temperature and the eluent was monitored at 220 nm using detector. The mobile phase of 0.1 % Formic acid: Phosphate Buffer pH 4.8: Methanol 60:15:25% v/v mixture at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min was used as a mobile phase. The injection volume was 20 μ l.

Fig. 2 Optimized Chromatogram of Acebrophylline & Erdosteine in 0.1% Formic acid: Phosphate Buffer pH 4.8: Methanol 60:15:25% v/v.

Forced Degradation Study

1) Acid Degradation

Fig. 3: Chromatogram of Acid Degradation on Sample.

2) Base Degradation

Fig. 4: Chromatogram of Base Degradation on Sample.

3) Oxidation Degradation

Fig. 5: Chromatogram of Oxidative Degradation on Sample.

4) Photolytic Degradation

Fig. 6: Chromatogram of Photolytic Degradation Standard and Sample.

5) Thermal Degradation

Fig. 7: Chromatogram of Thermal Degradation Standard and Sample.

Table 2: Forced degradation summary of Acebrophylline and Erdosteine.

Acebrophylline Standard Area		27410
Degradation Condition	Area after degradation	% Degradation
Acid	22740	17.0
Base	24100	12.1
Peroxide	25620	7.0
Thermal	23275	15.1
Photo	26262	4.0
Erdosteine Standard Area		10203
Acid	8607	16.0
Base	9133	10.0
Peroxide	8785	14.0
Thermal	9481	7.0
Photo	9946	3.0

Validation of RP-HPLC method

Linearity

Linearity was assessed by preparing five solutions of Acebrophylline and Erdosteine. The method demonstrated linearity over the concentration range of 500-1500 µg/ml with a correlation coefficient ($R^2 = 0.9999$).

Table 3: Linearity Data for Acebrophylline and Erdosteine.

Acebrophylline	
Concentration (µg/mL)	Peak Area (n=5)
500	13760.67
750	20683.02

1000	27448.97
1250	34394.32
1500	41353.63
Linear Regression Equation	$Y = 27.5588x - 30.7718$
Regression Coefficient (R²)	$R^2 = 0.9999$
Erdosteine	
500	5105.57
750	7664.39
1000	10212.72
1250	12737.43
1500	15334.78
Linear Regression Equation	$Y = 10.2125x - 1.6044$
Regression Coefficient (R²)	$R^2 = 0.9999$

Fig. 8: Calibration Curve of Acebrophylline and Erdosteine.

Fig. 9: Overlay of Linearity Chromatogram of Acebrophylline and Erdosteine Precision.

Table 4: Repeatability Data Acebrophylline and Erdosteine.

Sr. No.	Acebrophylline 1000.0 µg/mL	Erdosteine 1000.0 µg/mL
1	27448.64	10212.72
2	27445.90	10210.62

3	27438.52	10216.35
4	27441.05	10209.66
5	27443.14	10211.49
6	27440.01	10213.56
Mean	27442.87	10212.398
SD	3.821	2.388
%RSD	0.014	0.023

Table 5: Intraday and Inter Day Precision Data of Acebrophylline.

Precision	Intraday		Interday	
	Acebrophylline	Erdosteine	Acebrophylline	Erdosteine
Drug	500		500	
	1000		1000	
	1500		1500	
Concentration (µg/ml)	500		500	
	1000		1000	
	1500		1500	
Mean peak area ± SD (n = 3)	13758.851 ± 2.120	5103.407 ± 2.280	13764.165 ± 1.950	5105.932 ± 1.260
	27447.444 ± 2.472	10212.076 ± 1.951	27442.719 ± 2.820	10214.528 ± 2.119
	41351.455 ± 2.365	15333.513 ± 2.288	41353.207 ± 3.274	15335,259 ± 2.144
% RSD	0.015	0.044	0.014	0.025
	0.009	0.019	0.010	0.021
	0.006	0.015	0.008	0.014

Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantitation (LOQ)

Using slope and Y-intercept, the determined values of LOD and LOQ were evaluated. LOD and LOQ value for Acebrophylline was found to be 7.276 µg/ml and 22.047 µg/ml respectively. LOD and LOQ value for Erdosteine was found to be 6.091 µg/ml and 18.459 µg/ml respectively.

Accuracy (n=3)

Accuracy of the method was confirmed by recovery study at three levels (80%, 100% and 120%) of placebo addition.

Table 6: Accuracy Data of Acebrophylline.

Level of Spiking	Amount of Drug Present (µg/mL)	Amount of drug added (µg/mL)	Amount of Drug recovered (µg/mL)	% Recovery	Avg. %Recovery	% RSD
80 %	1000	800	800.45	100.06	100.10	0.13
	1000	800	801.99	100.25		
	1000	800	800.01	100.00		
100%	1000	1000	1000.67	100.07	100.02	0.10
	1000	1000	999.04	99.90		

	1000	1000	1000.96	100.10		
120%	1000	1200	1200.77	100.06	100.07	0.05
	1000	1200	1200.30	100.03		
	1000	1200	1201.41	100.12		

Table 7: Accuracy Data of Erdosteine.

Level of Spiking	Amount of Drug Present ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Amount of drug added ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Amount of Drug recovered ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	% Recovery	Avg. %Recovery	% RSD
80 %	1000	800	800.88	100.11	100.01	0.10
	1000	800	799.29	99.91		
	1000	800	800.12	100.02		
100%	1000	1000	1000.18	100.02	99.98	0.04
	1000	1000	999.37	99.94		
	1000	1000	999.73	99.97		
120%	1000	1200	1200.44	100.04	100.00	0.04
	1000	1200	1199.55	99.96		
	1000	1200	1200.01	100.00		

Robustness

Table 8: Robustness Data of Acebrophylline.

Parameter	Level of change	Area	Mean	%SD	%RSD
Flow rate (± 0.02)	-0.02	26887.578	26835.446	46.450	0.173
		26820.302			
		26798.459			
	+0.02	28414.447	28458.593	39.183	0.138
		28489.247			
		28472.084			
pH (± 2)	-2	28189.478	28166.017	61.232	0.217
		28096.523			
		28212.049			
	+2	28502.981	28500.211	35.647	0.125
		28463.259			
		28534.392			
Mobile Phase composition (± 2)	-2	26389.243	26326.820	219.804	0.835
		26508.661			
		26082.557			
	+2	29794.352	29704.376	282.301	0.950
		29930.723			
		29388.054			

Table 9: Robustness Data of Erdosteine.

Parameter	Level of change	Area	Mean	%SD	%RSD
Flow rate (± 0.02)	-0.02	93789.147	93711.942	88.111	0.094
		93615.954			
		93730.724			

	+0.02	12808.478	12806.971	1.862	0.015
		12804.889			
		12807.547			
pH (± 2)	-2	12789.548	12626.895	155.275	1.230
		12480.236			
		12610.902			
	+2	12990.118	12943.892	45.561	0.352
		12899.026			
		12942.531			
Mobile Phase composition (± 2)	-2	13095.225	13280.819	186.085	1.401
		13467.391			
		13279.840			
	+2	15522.321	15355.461	180.268	1.174
		15164.259			
		15379.804			

Assay of Synthetic Mixture

Applicability of the proposed method was tested by analyzing the Synthetic Mixture. Results as % Assay is shown in Table 6.18.

Table 10: Assay of Synthetic Mixture (Acebrophylline & Erdosteine).

Drug	Area of Sample	%Assay	%Avg. Assay	% SD	% RSD
Acebrophylline	27502.239	99.938	100.206	0.233	0.232
	27611.371	100.335			
	27614.771	100.347			
Erdosteine	10189.147	100.030	100.154	0.140	0.139
	10199.011	100.127			
	10217.186	100.305			

These results indicates that the developed method is specific, accurate, precise, simple, sensitive, robust and rapid.

CONCLUSION

Based on the experimental results, the proposed method is accurate, novel, simple, precise, linear, sensitive, robust, and stable for the estimation of Acebrophylline and Erdosteine in synthetic mixtures.

REFERENCES

1. Kumar V., Abbas A.K., Aster J.C. Robbins and Cotran Pathologic Basis of Disease, 10th Edition, Elsevier, 2020; 457.
2. Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (GOLD), "Global Strategy for the Diagnosis, Management, and Prevention of COPD", October 2025; <https://goldcopd.org>

3. Murray JF, Nadel JA, Broaddus VC, Mason RJ. Murray and Nadel's Textbook of Respiratory Medicine, 6th Edition, Elsevier, 2016; 1025.
4. Cazzola M, Calzetta L, Page CP, et al. "Pharmacology and therapeutic potential of Erdosteine and related drugs," *Pulmonary Pharmacology & Therapeutics*, 2010; 23(2): 99–114.
5. Sharma Bhavik and Agarwal Sushil Kumar, "RP-HPLC Method Development and Validation for Estimation of Acebrophylline", *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical research and Development*, 2018; 6(6): 50-55.
6. Patel A et al., "Development and Validation of UV Spectroscopic Method for Estimation of Acebrophylline In Tablet Dosage Form." *Am. J. PharmTech Res.*, 2019; 09.
7. Nakarani Pradip P. and Patel Dhaval M., "Development and Validation of Stability indicating RP-HPLC method for Estimation of Acebrophylline in their Dosage form." *International Journal of Pharmacy Research and Technology*, 2013; 3: 01-04.
8. Bertolini, T., Vicentini, L., Boschetti, S. *et al.* A Novel Ultra-High Performance Liquid Chromatography Method for the Determination of Erdosteine, Related Impurities and Degradation Products in New Effervescent Tablets. *Chromatographia*, 2018; 81: 1661–1672.
9. Mohanrao Tammishetty and Reddy Challa Balasekhara, "A New Investigational Method for Quantification and Validation of Analytical method for Cefixime and Erdosteine by UPLC with Photo Diode Array Detector in Bulk formulation." *Indian Drugs*, 2020; 57(11): 52.
10. ICH Harmonized Tripartite Guideline, "Validation of Analytical Procedures", Text and Methodology Q2 (R2), October 2025; <https://www.ich.org/page/quality-guidelines>